

FORMATION OF LEARNING STYLES OF SCHOOLCHILDREN IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract: The article discusses some learning styles of schoolchildren in English lessons and ways of their formation. The features of these styles are analyzed.

Key words: learning styles, tasks, algorithmic style, gaming style, translation style, research style, combinatorial style.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada ingliz tili darslarida foydalaniladigan ayrim o'qitish uslublari ko'rib chiqilgan. Mazkur uslublarning xususiyatlari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qitish uslublari, topshiriqlar, algoritmik uslub, o'yin uslubi, tarjima uslubi, tadqiqot uslubi, kombinatorlik uslubi.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрены некоторые стили учения школьников на уроках английского языка и пути их формирования. Проанализированы особенности этих стилей.

Ключевые слова: стили учения, задания, алгоритмический стиль, игровой стиль, переводческий стиль, исследовательский стиль, комбинаторный стиль.

Introduction. In the process of teaching English, the uniform and continuous use of didactic material that forms various styles contributes to an increase in the intellectual activity of schoolchildren. The manifestation of a student's personal cognitive style at a given level of his development in a specific learning situation is called a learning style [3].

Literature analysis. The term “learning style,” introduced in the 70s of the twentieth century, denoted a person’s typical approach to the learning process. M.A. Kholodnaya understands learning styles as “learning strategies that characterize an individual’s response to the demands of a specific learning situation”[8]. These are individual ways of learning activities. E.A. Bogdanova identified and characterized algorithmic, translational, applied, deductive, intuitive, combinatorial, research and game learning styles [2]. The formation of the same learning styles for younger schoolchildren in English lessons was considered by E.N. Kibireva [6; 7]. She also revealed the teacher’s methods of developing the personal cognitive style of a primary school student when learning a foreign language.

Results. In English lessons, the following teaching styles are formed: 1) algorithmic style - execution of actions in a strict sequence according to a model; 2) translation style - finding correspondences, recoding; 3) deductive style - obtaining knowledge through logical conclusions; 4) combinatorial style - classification according to certain characteristics; 5) applied style - acquiring knowledge in practice and communicative situations; 6) play style - learning through play; 7) intuitive style - discovery of new knowledge using guessing mechanisms; 8) research style - search-problem activity.

In the process of our research, we identified the possibilities of forming a student’s personal cognitive style when learning a foreign language through the use of specially designed didactic tasks. Here we will look at some learning styles when studying the subject "English".

Algorithmic style. An algorithm is a clear sequence of actions aimed at obtaining a specific result. A person performs actions according to a given pattern, in an established order. Words, phrases, and sentences are built on the algorithmic principle from morphemes and syllables. An example of an algorithm would be the fixed order of words in sentences and phrases in the English language, the order of letters in words. Regarding teaching English, algorithms are used when teaching all types of speech activities at the stage of familiarization with language material, as

well as at the stage of training all types of speech activities (reading, writing, speaking, listening). Tasks aimed at developing an algorithmic learning style are necessary to automate the skills of language and speech activity [7]: 1. Make sentences based on the model. 2. Listen and repeat. 3. Complete according to the model.

Game style. In the life of schoolchildren, especially children of primary school age, play plays an important role. The game style in English lessons is a conditional reproduction by participants of real practical activities of people, creating conditions for real communication. “The game motivates speech activity, since students seem to find themselves in a situation where the need to say something, ask, find out, prove, or share something with the interlocutor is actualized” [6]. Choosing the right game is one of the most important tasks of a foreign language teacher. This choice should be made taking into account the age characteristics of the students. The teacher directs and controls the course of the game. There are different types of games that shape the play style of learning.

For example, didactic games occupy one of the first places in foreign language classes as a form of oral development of schoolchildren. Playing lotto promotes strong mastery of lexical material. The child gradually moves from a visual, effective way of mastering vocabulary (the teacher names the subject in English, showing it) to a dictionary-figurative one (the teacher constructs different types of sentences about the subject that does not exist at the moment). There are also educational games such as “edible - inedible”, dominoes, “find the odd one out” and others.

Translation style involves interpretation, translation of information from one qualitative characteristic to another, decoding, interpretation, search for correspondence. Interpretation is a translation from one language to another (verbal, symbolic, internal human language) and it is associated with understanding, as it helps to establish connections between the objects under consideration [2].

When learning a foreign language, the process of interpreting information plays a vital role, since throughout the entire training a search for correspondence

between the source language and the target language occurs. I.A. Zimnyaya [5] believes that a person's linguistic base, in the process of development and mastery of their native language, directly interacts with the development of the thinking apparatus. A person's acquisition of another language can be considered as a process of interaction between two language codes. Teaching a second foreign language is teaching the rules of conversion from the native language to a foreign language. E.A. Bogdanova [2] identifies the following methods of encoding information: verbal (verbal - printed and handwritten TEXT); geometric (visual, visual, figurative - illustration, FIGURE, diagram, table, etc.); formulaic (symbolic, symbolic - designation, FORMULA, etc.); substantive-practical (construction of diagrams) The tasks that form the translation style of teaching are very diverse and may include [2]:

1. verbal method - tests, answers to questions from the text, coming up with a title for the text, correlating spoken speech with written text;
2. geometric method - drawing up sentences based on graphic models, composing phrases, sentences, stories based on pictures, drawing illustrations for the text read;
3. formulaic method - reading by transcription, correlating letters and sounds;
4. subject-practical method - constructing a model of a sentence, a diagram of syllables and words.

The ability to translate information from one language to another usually makes it possible to understand and comprehend the information, so it is necessary to pay great attention to translations and tasks aimed at developing a translation style. Examples of tasks: 1) Read the story, replacing the pictures with words. 2) Match the picture and the word. 3) Read the text and choose the correct answer to the question.[7]

Research style. Research always involves a high degree of independent activity. Research activity is inextricably linked with the concept of "cognitive independence," which implies "the ability to understand a question, a task and find ways to solve them, a critical mind and the ability to draw conclusions, highlight

what is essential, and most importantly, the ability to express one's point of view, regardless of the judgments of others" [4]. In English lessons, in order to develop an investigative teaching style, it is advisable to structure the lesson in such a way, to create such situations so that the student can defend his point of view, build hypotheses, and argue his opinion. For example, when studying works of folk art, you can conduct a comparative analysis of the heroes of a fairy tale, study what these heroes have in common and how they differ. When studying vocabulary, you can conduct research work according to the plan:

1. The word and its lexical meaning (working with a dictionary);
2. The word and its "relatives" are words with the same root;
3. Synonyms and antonyms;
4. The word in phraseological units.

Thanks to this type of activity, children learn to work with dictionaries, reference books and Internet resources. In the process of further education, you can teach children to collect and organize data by maintaining thematic dictionaries. This type of activity increases the level of mastering English vocabulary.

You can also use tasks such as reading and listening to extract specific information, observation, finding similarities and differences in pictures, and questioning. When using research assignments, it is important to present the result of the work done in the form of a report or presentation.

The combinatorial style of learning involves tasks aimed at developing this style, focused on developing the skills of sorting, classifying, and listing. In the English language there are such types of classification as phonetic, grammatical, lexical, syntactic. In speech situations, classification also takes place when words are combined by meaning, by speech context, by communicative situation.

Tasks aimed at developing a combinatorial learning style are designed to teach how to combine, classify, and systematize. These can be tasks for sorting objects (compiling lists, tables), composing a whole from disparate elements (composing phrases, sentences), classification according to a certain criterion. Examples of tasks:

1) make up phrases; 2) make up the longest word from the given letters; 3) make as many words as possible from one word; 4) Englishman Johnny is going to school after the holidays. He goes to the supermarket to do some shopping. Help him choose the things he needs for school: a fox, a bear, a rabbit, a pen, a pencil, books, a bag, a cat, a dog. Name the group of these objects in one word.

Conclusion. Awareness of the demand for a foreign language in the modern world and its role in the labor market helps to increase the motivation of schoolchildren to study it from a very early age. This, in turn, actualizes the search for ways to improve the teaching of foreign languages.

Currently, there is a need to supplement the content of training with methods that would contribute to the development of the personality of each student in the process of collective learning. This problem is directly related to the developments of pedagogical science in the field of personal cognitive style, namely the formation of a personal cognitive style in each child based on the actualization and enrichment of the entire system of mechanisms of stylistic behavior, taking into account the specifics of his mental experience, and the formation of multi-style intellectual behavior.

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